

Impact of E-service quality on E-loyalty with the moderating effect of E-satisfaction of youngsters using E-commerce platforms, an empirical evidence from Shopee in Vietnam

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Abstract

This study measures the influence of e-service quality on e-satisfaction, thereby affecting the e-loyalty of young people when shopping online on Shopee Vietnam. The purpose of this study is to provide knowledge to better understand the most important aspects of e-service quality that affect youth satisfaction, thereby affecting loyalty. This study uses qualitative research method combined with quantitative research method. The study conducted a survey on 250 users of Shopee e-commerce site. The results show that e-service quality has a significant impact on e-satisfaction in using the Shopee e-commerce platform, and satisfaction has an impact on loyalty. In which, the factor that has the greatest impact on e-satisfaction is Fulfillment.

Keywords: *E-service quality, E-loyalty, E-satisfaction, E-commerce platforms, youngsters, Shopee Vietnam.*

1. Introduction

The e-commerce market in Vietnam in particular and the world in general is growing gradually. Many businesses have gradually shifted from traditional business to e-commerce business, or a combination of both methods. Shopee.com.vn is an e-commerce platform with the largest market share in Vietnam. Shopee is one of the e-commerce sites where buyers and sellers can message to exchange, consult, ask questions before buying. The objective of this study is to study the factors of e-service quality affecting the satisfaction of young consumers and the impact of this satisfaction on their loyalty. To the knowledge of the authors, there are currently many research articles on this field, however, there are very few research articles on the impact of e-service quality on e-satisfaction, and e-satisfaction affect e-loyalty with the case study of Shopee in Vietnam. At the same time, previous studies did not focus on young people in Vietnam.

2. Literature review

2.1. E-service quality

According to Zeithaml et al. (2018), e-service quality is defined as a complete analysis of how customers perceive the services offered based on their involvement and loyalty. It is also viewed as a competitive factor in differentiating from other businesses/competitors. High e-service quality is therefore thought to boost a company's long-term profitability (Ghobadian et al., 1994). How well the offered services meet the needs of the customers serves as a gauge of an e-quality. service's Customers' expectations of what they would receive after making a purchase lead to the perception that the service is of a high quality (Ghobadian et al., 1994). With this, it is concluded that the success of B2C e-commerce is significantly dependent on the quality of e-service (Bhatti et al., 2002; Delone & Mclean 2003).

In order to evaluate the quality of e-services, Wolfinbarger & Gilly (2003) developed the "comQ" scaling, which takes into account the website's design, fulfillment/reliability, customer assistance, and security/privacy. First, website design incorporates relevant design aspects from Holloway and Beatty (2008) and Chang et al., as well as personalization-related components (2009). Second, fulfillment/reliability is based on Nilsson and Wall (2017) and refers to the timely and accurate delivery of goods that are accurately represented and in good condition. Third, confidence in the website is necessary for security and privacy (Ranganathan, 2002; Blut, 2016). Following that, customer service is modified from Nilsson and Wall (2017)

and Chang et al. (2009), which emphasizes a combination of interest in problem-solving, a personal willingness to assist, and a prompt response to inquiries.

2.2. E-satisfaction

An appropriate response for states that want to buy is satisfaction (Chang, 2008). Additionally, client experiences at various phases of the purchasing process influence satisfaction (Lin, 2011). E-satisfaction incorporates customer evaluations of their online experiences in order to compare them to their experiences with traditional service providers or retail establishments (Rachjaibun, 2007). Customer loyalty was studied by Srinivasan and Anderson in the context of e-commerce, and according to their definition, it is a good attitude toward online shopping that encourages repeat purchasing. They also looked into how customers' loyalty is affected by their pleasure with an e-commerce company, and their findings suggested that customers' contentment is influenced by their most recent shopping experience with that company (Anderson, 2003).

2.3. E-loyalty

E-loyalty involves a favorable customer tendency toward online retail, and its outcome is a repeat of the purchasing activity. Customers' e-loyalty differs significantly from that of traditional environments since Internet users can visit websites with just a click (Jeon, 2009). One of the key factors in e-success commerce's is consumer loyalty (Rachjaibun, 2007). Oliver demonstrated a loyalty framework based on the recognition-effect-effort pattern in the real world of business in 1997. This model consists of a series of stages, starting with recognition (loyalty to information like price and qualities), followed by effect (loyalty to interests), effort (loyalty to tendency), and finally action (loyalty to action). According to Oliver, customers first develop a loyalty for the sensation of recognition before extending it to the idea of consequence.

2.4. E-flatforms

Concerning permitting B2C e-commerce shopping, there has been debate over the effectiveness and efficiency of quality in the e-service (Zeithaml et al., 2002). Additionally, Patterson and Yu (2006) refer to customer engagements as a physical and emotional connection made between a B2C e-commerce site's customers. Customer engagement is encouraged and raised when a customer uses e-services to purchase goods or services (Verleye et al., 2013; Baldus et al., 2015; Roy, 2018). Superior e-services' quality can have a favorable impact on customers' engagement (Chenet et al., 2010; Rossmann et al., 2016). Therefore, it will lead to positive customer involvement for B2C online shopping.

3. Research method

3.1. Conceptual model and hypotheses

The E-service quality dimensions have been categorized and evaluated as independent variables that influence satisfaction based on the context of this research and with reference to prior empirical studies. We identify the dimensions of E-service quality that impact E-satisfaction using the various mergers described in the approach section, and we put forth the following hypothesis.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Source: The author's

- H1: Website design is positively related to E-satisfaction.
- H2: Customer service is positively related to E-satisfaction.
- H3: Security is positively related to E-satisfaction.
- H4: Fulfillment is positively related to E-satisfaction.
- H5: E-satisfaction is positively related to E-loyalty.

3.2. Research design

The research approach chosen for the study has been detailed in this part. The nature of this investigation is quantitative. The quantitative strategy has been used in the design of the survey investigation. Additionally, this study used a single-method survey technique. Structured surveys with open-ended questions and various possible answers are the main tool for gathering data.

Moving on, it should be noted that the group from which researchers hope to gauge Service quality levels and the connection between E-service quality, E-customer satisfaction, and E-Loyalty includes Vietnamese internet users who engage in online shopping.

Convenience sampling was chosen as the sampling method for this study. Convenience sampling was chosen because of the data collection's apparent homogeneity, relative randomness, and sizeable sample size. The questionnaires were distributed electronically to internet and broadband users via emails and social media. In terms of sample size, the researchers distributed questionnaires to 295 people who are in the 15-35 age group, and 250 of them provided valid responses, yielding a response rate of 84.7 percent. Additionally, AMOS has been used for data analysis to evaluate the hypotheses using structural equation modeling (SEM). The scales used in this study were created by adapting those from earlier research on the topic. A 5-point Likert scale was used to collect responses. (Strongly Agree = 5, Strongly Disagree = 1).

The scales' original forms were converted from English to Vietnamese in two steps. First, all scales were independently translated into Vietnamese by two academics and two translation specialists with strong English language skills. The translations were then evaluated by a researcher and a translation specialist, and the best translations were chosen for acceptance. The scale expressions were finally approved after being double-checked by two academicians who are subject-matter specialists.

4. Data analysis and findings

4.1. Frequency & descriptive analysis of demographic factors

Table 1. Frequency & descriptive analysis of demographic factors

Criteria	Frequency	Percent
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Gender	Male	98	39.2%
	Female	152	60.8%
Average monthly salary	1 – 5 Million VND	40	16%
	5 – 10 Million VND	35	14%
	10 – 15 Million VND	101	40,4%
	15 – 30 Million VND	68	27,2%
	Higher than 30 million VND	6	2,4%
Age of respondents	15-20 age group	40	16%
	20-25 age group	80	32%
	25-30 age group	55	22%
	30-35 age group	60	24%

(Source: research of the authors)

The characteristics of the respondents from which the data were gathered are shown in Table 4.1, including gender, age, and monthly wage. According to the demographic statistics of the research sample, females make up the vast majority, the percentage of people with an average monthly income is 10-15 million, and people in the age group of 20–25 years old account for the largest proportion.

4.2. Reliability Testing

Using the Cronbach alpha coefficient, reliability can be assessed. If the alpha value is greater than 0.7, the reliability is good; if it is between 0.5 and 0.7, the reliability is medium. The questionnaire is not reliable if the alpha value is less than 0.5. In this study, the Cronbach alpha coefficient and SPSS version 26 were used to assess the reliability of the questionnaires.

Table 2. Reliable testing

Variable	Indicator	Factor Loading	Valid
Website design (WD) Cronbach Alpha = 0.869	WD1	0.305	Valid
	WD2	0.498	Valid
	WD3	0.410	Valid
	WD4	0.503	Valid
	WD5	0.497	Valid
	WD6	0.389	Valid
	WD7	0.324	Valid
Customer service (CS) Cronbach Alpha = 0.798	CS1	0.469	Valid
	CS2	0.321	Valid
	CS3	0.385	Valid
	CS4	0.466	Valid
	CS5	0.302	Valid
	CS6	0.344	Valid
Security (S) Cronbach Alpha = 0.696	S1	0.504	Valid
	S2	0.499	Valid
	S3	0.431	Valid
	S4	0.387	Valid
	S5	0.343	Valid
Fulfillment (F) Cronbach Alpha = 0.767	F1	0.505	Valid
	F2	0.499	Valid
	F3	0.301	Valid
	F4	0.322	Valid
	F5	0.345	Valid
E-Satisfaction (ES) Cronbach Alpha = 0.758	ES1	0.333	Valid
	ES2	0.431	Valid
	ES3	0.505	Valid

Variable	Indicator	Factor Loading	Valid
E-Loyalty (EL) Cronbach Alpha = 0.805	ES4	0.469	Valid
	EL1	0.785	Valid
	EL2	0.468	Valid
	EL3	0.771	Valid
	EL4	0.665	Valid

(Source: research of the authors)

All the scales has Cronbach Alpha >0.6. This outcome reflects the appropriateness and acceptability of the questionnaire's dependability. The table below displays this value. The research model was examined using structural equation modeling.

The factor loading value of the research variable indicators is the convergent validity value. If an indicator has an outer loading value larger than 0.7, convergent validity is required. The outcomes of each indicator's convergent validity test for the research variable are listed below. It is said that all indicators are valid based on the aforementioned facts. As a result, following study can employ all indications. The value of the cross-loading factor, which is used to compare the loading values of the desired construct and other constructs—which must be greater—to see if a construct has the right discriminant—indicates the value of discriminant validity.

As a result, all scales have a Cronbach Alpha coefficient that ranges from 0.696 to 0.869. Therefore, the scales' reliability is often good (Nunnally, J.C. and Bernstein, I.H. (1994).

4.3. Exploratory factor analysis

Table 3. Exploratory factor analysis

Indicator	Variable					
	WD	CS	S	F	ES	EL
WD1	0.506					
WD2	0.853					
WD3	0.719					
WD4	0.799					
WD5	0.865					
WD6	0.497					
WD7	0.555					
CS1		0.567				
CS2		0.766				
CS3		0.872				
CS4		0.541				
CS5		0.462				
CS6		0.651				
S1			0.403			
S2			0.506			
S3			0.611			
S4			0.721			
S5			0.547			
F1				0.466		
F2				0.558		
F3				0.601		
F4				0.489		
F5				0.545		
ES1					0.444	
ES2					0.567	
ES3					0.504	
ES4					0.498	

Indicator	Variable					
	WD	CS	S	F	ES	EL
EL1						0.676
EL2						0.545
EL3						0.647
EL4						0.531

(Source: research of the authors)

All indicators are valid, according to the information in the table above. As a result, following study can employ all indications. According to the conditions listed above, it can be concluded from the table above that all research variables have good dependability. Consequently, depending on the outcomes of the tests that have been performed. The results show that all observed variables when included in the analysis are divided into 6 groups. Factor loading coefficients of all observed variables are greater than 0.4 (Hair et al, 2010).

4.4. Hypothesis analysis

The Chi-square fit test and degree of freedom, CFI (Comparative Fit Index), RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation), TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index), RNI (Relative Noncentrality Index), NNFI (Non-Formed Fit Index), and IFI are the goodness of fit indices that were looked at in the study (Incremental Fit Index).

Table 4. Values of Fit and Goodness

Fit Index	Value	Good Fit Values	Acceptable fit values	Result
Chi square/df	2153.149/576=3.7	<3	<5	Acceptable
CFI	0.915	>0.95	>0.90	Acceptable
RMSEA	0.070	<0.050	<0.080	Acceptable
TLI	0.908	>0.95	>0.90	Acceptable
RNI	0.916	>0.95	>0.90	Acceptable
NNFI	0.907	>0.95	>0.90	Acceptable
IFI	0.914	>0.95	>0.90	Acceptable

(Source: research of the authors)

The study's goodness of fit values are displayed in Table 4. Examining the results reveals that all goodness of fit values exhibit a suitable fit. This circumstance suggests that the data gathered and the suggested model are compatible (Hair et al, 2010).

Table 5. Structural Equation Model Analysis

Hypothesis	Standardized β	p	Support/ Rejection
H1: Website design is positively related to E-satisfaction.	0.116	0.002	Supported
H2: Customer service is positively related to E-satisfaction.	0.243	0.000	Supported
H3: Security is positively related to E-satisfaction.	0.104	0.001	Supported
H4: Fulfillment is positively related to E-satisfaction.	0.303	0.000	Supported
H5: E-satisfaction is positively related to E-loyalty.	0.278	0.002	Supported

(Source: research of the authors)

In the structural model in Table 5, the hypothesis could be accepted if the coefficient value is positive and the p-value <0.05. It can be inferred from the findings that H1, H2, H3, H4 and H5 were accepted due to a positive coefficient value, p-value <0.05.

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model

(Source: research of the authors)

Figure 2 displays the correlations between the variables and the R2 value (**p <0.05, ***p<0.001). As a result, website design, customer service, security, and fulfillment, each account for 79% of satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.79$). While satisfaction was 79% explained by these factors ($R^2=0.79$), 21% of it was explained by other factors.

5. Conclusion

The study's findings indicate that the traditional idea of mediation—which links service quality, customer pleasure, and loyalty—can be used to explain phenomena in the e-commerce environment. Website design, customer service, security and fulfillment were the aspects of electronic service quality that, in the case of Shopee.com.vn, influenced electronic loyalty by mediating electronic satisfaction. Research results show that all factors of e-service quality including Website design, Customer service, Security and Fulfillment have a positive impact on customer satisfaction. In which, fulfillment has the greatest impact on customer satisfaction, Customer service has the second biggest impact on customer satisfaction, followed by website design. However, security has a negligible impact on customer satisfaction. In addition, e-satisfaction also has a positive effect on customer loyalty.

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